

1 **Anaerobic degradation of glycol ether-ethanol mixtures using EGSB**
2 **and hybrid reactors: performance comparison and ether cleavage**
3 **pathway**

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Graphical Abstracts

Highlights

- Anaerobic treatment is feasible for the removal of 1-ethoxy-2-propanol from water
- The hybrid reactor showed a solid retention capacity of 92% higher than control
- Hybrid and control reactors showed similar performances with global efficiencies >90%
- The detected byproducts clarified the degradation pathway of studied glycol ethers

18 **Abstract**

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3 19 The anaerobic biodegradation of ethanol-glycol ether mixtures as 1-ethoxy-2-
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5 20 propanol (E2P) and 1-methoxy-2-propanol (M2P), widely used in printing facilities,
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7 21 was investigated by means of two laboratory-scale anaerobic bioreactors at 25°C-an
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9 22 expanded granular sludge bed (EGSB) reactor and an anaerobic hybrid reactor (AHR)
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11 23 which incorporated a packed bed to improve biomass retention. Despite AHR showed
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13 24 almost half of solid leakages compared to EGSB, both reactors obtained practically the
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15 25 same performance for the operating conditions studied with global removal efficiencies
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17 26 (REs) higher than 92% for organic loading rates (OLRs) as high as 54 kg of chemical
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19 27 oxygen demand (COD) m⁻³ d⁻¹ (REs of 70% and 100% for OLRs of 10.6 and 8.3 kg
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21 28 COD m⁻³ d⁻¹ for E2P and M2P, respectively). Identified byproducts allowed clarifying
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23 29 the anaerobic degradation pathways of these glycol ethers. Thus, this study shows that
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25 30 anaerobic scrubber can be a feasible treatment for printing emissions.
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32 31 **Keywords: 1-ethoxy-2-propanol degradation; 1-methoxy-2-propanol**
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34 32 **degradation; anaerobic biotreatment; biomass retention capacity; printing**
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36 33 **industry wastewater**
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1. Introduction

Solvents are commonly used in packaging printing industries as ink components that are dried through evaporation, which are the sources of volatile organic compounds (VOCs) in air emissions throughout the printing process. These emissions show ethanol as the main solvent, which is used in many solvent-based inks, but other solvents such as glycol ethers are also predominantly identified (Bravo et al., 2017; Sempere et al., 2012). The glycol ethers that are present in these emissions are 1-ethoxy-2-propanol (E2P) and/or 1-methoxy-2-propanol (M2P) that are frequently used as retarders in the printing process (Cheremisinoff, 2003). Several regulations and guidelines have been established in many countries for the control of the emissions of VOCs in printing industry. In the European Union, VOC concentrations of these emissions must comply with limit values ranging from 20 to 100 mg C Nm⁻³ (Council Directive 2010/75/EU), depending on printing activity (offset, rotogravure, flexography, etc.) and solvent consumption threshold (>15 or >25 tonnes per year). USA Environmental Protection Agency also recommends levels of control for these emissions ranging from 65 to 80% for overall control efficiency and from 90 to 95 % for control device efficiency, depending on installation date of equipment and printing activity. Many states and local agencies have adopted regulations for controlling emissions from printing industry consistent with these control levels (USEPA, 1978; USEPA, 2006). To fulfill these regulations and guidelines, the printing industry frequently needs end-of-pipe treatments of these emissions. In this regard, biological treatments such as biofiltration have been studied to remove volatile organic compounds from air emissions (Malhautier et al., 2005). A new alternative treatment based on an anaerobic bioscrubber has recently been described (Bravo et al., 2017; Waalkens et al., 2015). In this process, solvents are initially transferred from the gas phase to the liquid phase and subsequently degraded in

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60 an anaerobic reactor, where solvents are transformed into bioenergy in the form of
61 biogas. The anaerobic biodegradability of M2P was demonstrated by Lafita et al. (2015)
62 when working with an expanded granular sludge bed (EGSB) reactor at 25°C. The
63 removal efficiency (RE) of M2P reached up to 87% and showed a long lag phase that
64 took 34 days to remove more than 50% of M2P. A first evidence of anaerobic
65 degradation of M2P was reported by the European Chemicals Bureau (2006). In this
66 study, a batch test using inoculum from a municipal digester, only a removal efficiency
67 of 38% was observed after 81 days of operation.

68 Regarding the mechanism for the ether cleavage, it is not yet well understood, but
69 the most accepted mechanism for glycol ether cleavage includes a double H/OH
70 interchange (*transhydroxylation*), resulting in the *gem*-diol intermediate (Speranza et
71 al., 2002; White et al., 1996), which rapidly collapses to the carbonyl or the keto group.
72 In the anaerobic degradation of polyethylene glycol (PEG), migration of hydroxyl group
73 generates an intermediate hemiacetal leading to acetaldehyde. Thus, degradation of the
74 polymer occurs by successive eliminations of acetaldehyde units catalyzed by a
75 cobalamin-dependent intracellular enzyme (PEG acetaldehyde lyase), according to the
76 following reaction (Frings et al., 1992):

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78 Kawai (2002) hypothesized that the metabolism of polypropylene glycol (with
79 identical terminal OH group as M2P and E2P) is the same as that of PEG. By analogy,
80 Lafita et al. (2015) proposed the same mechanism for the degradation of M2P, in this
81 case leading to methanol and acetone or propionaldehyde.

82 Biological treatments have been shown to be capable to remove slowly
83 biodegradable industrial compounds (Zhang et al., 2016: T., Huang, 2017). Among

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84 these, anaerobic reactors based on granular sludge technology have become interesting
85 options for the cost-effective and sustainable treatment of industrial wastewaters (Petta
86 et al., 2017; Delforno et al., 2016). In this sense, the high contact between wastewater
87 and biofilm that is promoted by expanding the sludge bed makes the EGSB a suitable
88 technology to treat high stress, less biodegradable or toxic components in wastewater.
89 Expanding the granular sludge requires high upflow velocity (v_{up}) that can produce the
90 wash-out of granular biomass from the reactor (Dries et al., 1998). This wash-out
91 phenomenon can also be caused by a low-concentrate substrate (Puñal et al., 2003);
92 wastewaters containing fat, oil, and grease (Jeganathan et al., 2006); or the combination
93 of organic overload and daily interruption in the substrate supply (Lafita et al., 2015).

94 To improve biomass retention, Guiot and van den Berg (1985) used an anaerobic
95 hybrid reactor (AHR) in treating synthetic soluble sugar wastewater, where an upflow
96 anaerobic sludge bed (UASB) reactor was modified by adding an anaerobic filter in the
97 upper zone to replace the gas-liquid-solid (GLS) separator. The results showed the filter
98 as an inexpensive method to enhance biomass retention. This type of AHR offers
99 different advantages, such as higher biomass retention capacity, a polishing effect to the
100 effluent due to the biomass accumulated in the filter (Shivayogimath and Ramanujam,
101 1999), or a higher buffering effect against shock loading (McHugh et al., 2006).
102 Because of these characteristics, the AHR seems a promising and emerging alternative
103 that can be considered feasible for the treatment of (especially high-strength)
104 wastewaters from different industries. Thus, for wastewater from a distillery spent
105 wash, Shivayogimath and Ramanujam (1999) demonstrated that a hybrid reactor
106 combining a UASB reactor in the lower part with polypropylene pall rings filter media
107 in the upper part could treat high organic loading, such as 36 kg of chemical oxygen
108 demand (COD) $m^{-3}d^{-1}$, which was a very efficient GLS separator. The AHR also

109 showed high REs (up to 90.3%) in the treatment of a dairy industry effluent (Belançon
110 et al., 2010). Treating a chemical synthesis-based pharmaceutical wastewater, Oktem et
111 al. (2008) revealed that the AHR presented strong stability to changes in organic
112 loadings. McKeown et al. (2009) showed that the AHR had a suitable configuration for
113 long-term low-temperature treatment of acidified wastewaters.

114 The main purposes of this work were (i) to evaluate the feasibility of the anaerobic
115 biodegradation of wastewater containing solvents from a flexographic printing industry
116 by working with an AHR, including common glycol ethers such as M2P and E2P, and
117 (ii) to compare the operation performance and biomass retention capacity between the
118 AHR and the EGSB reactor. Furthermore, (iii) the study of the degradation of two
119 different glycol ethers such as E2P and M2P might be useful for an in-depth
120 understanding of the mechanisms involved in the anaerobic ether cleavage. Additionally
121 and to the best of the authors' knowledge, this research is the first study about E2P
122 degradation in an anaerobic reactor.

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124 2. Materials and Methods

125 2.1. Reactors' setup

126 Most of the experiments were performed in two anaerobic bioreactors, an EGSB
127 reactor (R1) and an AHR (R2). Fig. 1 shows a schematic diagram of both systems. The
128 EGSB diagram reactor was equivalent to the AHR but without the presence of the
129 packing material (Fig. 1, part 4 in R2). The upper part of the AHR, from 1.40 m to 1.57
130 m in height, was randomly packed with polyethylene rings (0.0254 m in diameter). Both
131 reactors had the same dimensions, with a sludge bed (Fig. 1, part 3) of 4 L (height of
132 1.205 m and internal diameter of 0.065 m) and a total volume of 19 L. In this paper,

133 organic load rate is calculated on the basis of this sludge bed effective volume (4L). The
134 supernatant reactor samples were taken at the recirculation port installed at a 1.60-m
135 height. The gas was conducted to a gas seal (Fig. 1, part 8) with a solution of NaOH to
136 remove H₂S and CO₂. The reactors' temperature was maintained at 25°C, with an
137 external jacket with water recirculation connected to a thermostat system (Polyscience
138 SD15R-30, USA). Each anaerobic system was equipped with two peristaltic pumps that
139 provided feeding and recirculation flows (Fig. 1, part 7) through the reactor. The
140 feeding (Fig. 1, part 1) and the recirculation were maintained at constant flows of 10 L
141 day⁻¹ and 32 L h⁻¹, respectively, to provide a v_{up} of 9.80 m h⁻¹ in the sludge bed and a v_{up}
142 of 0.98 m h⁻¹ in the fixed film section. The increment in the organic loading rate (OLR)
143 was carried out by increasing the COD concentration, keeping the feeding flow
144 constant. A second EGSB (R3), identical to R1, was also utilized in the last part of this
145 study to elucidate the reaction mechanism. For this purpose, an ethanol-acetone mixture
146 was used as the substrate.

2.2. Reactor operation

149 The reactors were started up by using anaerobic granular sludge (4 L) taken from a
150 local brewery wastewater treatment plant (Font Salem S. L., El Puig, Spain). Both R1
151 and R2 were operated for more than 300 days (Table 1), with influent buffered with 5 g
152 of NaHCO₃ L⁻¹; magnesium and calcium were maintained at 40 mg L⁻¹, and
153 macronutrients and micronutrients were added in proportion to the COD (Table 2). All
154 chemicals used were of analytical grade. The startup (stage S-I) of the reactors was
155 carried out in the first 90 days of the experimental period (Table 1). At this stage, the
156 OLR was increased from 9.1 to 47.0 kg COD m⁻³d⁻¹, with a readily biodegradable

157 substrate such as ethanol. From day 91 to day 202 (stage S-II), the influent composition
158 was changed to a binary mixture of ethanol and E2P with a mass ratio of 9:1, and the
159 average OLR was kept at 47.4 kg COD m⁻³d⁻¹. At stage S-III, from day 203 to day 221,
160 the OLR of E2P was increased to an ethanol-E2P mass ratio of 4:1, resulting in an OLR
161 of 54.1 kg COD m⁻³d⁻¹. At stage S-IV, from day 222 to day 230, the composition of the
162 influent was changed to a ternary mixture of ethanol, E2P, and M2P with a mass ratio of
163 8:1:1 to check if there would be no need for a period of adaptation for M2P degradation.
164 At this stage, the average OLR was 48.8 kg COD m⁻³d⁻¹. At stage S-V, from day 231 to
165 day 271, no feeding and no recirculation were applied to evaluate the effect of a long
166 starvation period that typically occurs in industrial facilities. At stage S-VI, from day
167 272 to day 305, a restartup was carried out with the same ternary mixture used at stage
168 S-IV and with the OLR range from 15.9 to 40.7 kg COD m⁻³d⁻¹. Finally, at stage S-VII,
169 from day 306 to day 335, the average OLR was 46.2 kg COD m⁻³d⁻¹, and the mass ratio
170 of the mixture of ethanol, E2P, and M2P was changed to 7:1:2.

171 The influent of the R3 reactor was buffered, and the micronutrients and the
172 macronutrients were added in the same way as in the previously described reactors. The
173 startup was carried out with ethanol until it reached almost complete substrate
174 degradation for an OLR of 25.0 kg COD m⁻³d⁻¹. Then, maintaining the OLR, the
175 feeding composition was changed to an ethanol-acetone mixture with a mass ratio of
176 1:1, and the reactor was operated for 27 days under these conditions.

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178 **2.3. Effluent and biogas analyses**

179 The COD, as well as volatile fatty acid (VFA), total suspended solid (TSS), and
180 volatile suspended solid (VSS) concentrations were analyzed according to Standard

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181 Methods (American Public Health Association, 1999). The NH_4^+ , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , K^+ , PO_4^{3-}
182 , and SO_4^{2-} concentrations were measured by ionic chromatography (883 Basic IC Plus,
183 Metrohm, Switzerland). The effluent's byproducts and solvents were identified by gas
184 chromatography-mass spectrometry (5973 N MS/GC Agilent Technologies, Spain). The
185 solvents in the effluent were determined by gas chromatography (Agilent GC 7890A,
186 Spain) equipped with flame ionization detector; the solvents and the byproducts of the
187 solvent degradation were separated on a Restek Rtx-VMS (USA) column (30 m long x
188 0.25 mm i.d. x 1.4 μm particle size), and helium was used as the carrier gas. The biogas
189 composition before the gas seal was determined by using a portable biogas analyzer
190 (COMBIMASS® GA-m, Binder, Germany). The methane flow rates of both reactors
191 were measured after H_2S and CO_2 in the gas seal were removed by a gas meter (MGC-
192 10 PMMA, Ritter, Germany). Conductivity and pH were determined by a precision
193 handheld meter (Multi 340i, WTW, Germany).

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194 The monitoring of bioreactors has been carried out from individual determinations,
195 average values and standard deviation have been considered for overall operation
196 conditions for each stage (Table 1).

198 3. Results and Discussion

199 3.1. Reactor performance

200 The evolution of the global performance of both reactors, R1 and R2, is plotted in
201 Fig. 2, where stages S-I to S-VII are indicated. The detailed evolution of the main
202 parameters of the system (pH, conductivity, COD inlet concentration, etc.) can be found
203 as supplementary material (Fig. S.1 to Fig. S.6). REs higher than 95% were achieved
204 during all startup periods (S-I), including when the OLR reached the maximum value of

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205 47.0 kg of COD $\text{m}^{-3}\text{d}^{-1}$, as can be observed in Fig. 2. This was a predictable behavior
206 since the organic substrate was ethanol, and the sludge came from a brewery wastewater
207 treatment plant, so the biomass was well adapted to this substrate. The VFA
208 concentrations were below 70 mg L^{-1} in the first 50 days, but when the OLR was
209 increased to 47.0 kg COD $\text{m}^{-3}\text{d}^{-1}$, the VFA concentrations reached values of 221.9 and
210 172.0 mg $\text{CH}_3\text{COOH L}^{-1}$ for R1 and R2, respectively. The minimal accumulation of
211 VFA can be attributed to the faster metabolism of acidogenic bacteria compared to
212 methanogenic archaea, but the VFA concentrations decreased when the high OLR was
213 maintained over time, reflecting the methanogenic population's adaptation to these
214 operational conditions. In any case, the VFA concentrations were always relatively low
215 ($< 250 \text{ mg CH}_3\text{COOH L}^{-1}$) in both reactors, indicating no significant kinetic decoupling
216 between the acidogenic and the methanogenic communities.

217 When E2P was included as a component of the influent at stage S-II (Table 1), the
218 total RE in both reactors dropped from 99% to 85%, but the RE was progressively
219 recovered to more than 95% (Fig. 2). This behavior can be explained by assuming that
220 the biomass was not adapted to E2P, so the biomass needed an acclimatization period to
221 be able to metabolize this substrate. This period could be related to the development of
222 ether-cleavage enzymes to degrade this substrate as suggested by Lafita et al. (2015).
223 This approach is shared by Chen et al. (2008) who point the induction of specific
224 enzymes as one of the mechanisms through which adaptation can occur. Various
225 anaerobic bacteria yielding rearrangements of carbon-carbon bonds via
226 transhydroxylation and depending on cobalamin were described for the degradation of
227 polyethylene glycol (Schink et al., 1992; Frings et al., 1992). It would seem plausible
228 that this same catalytic system governs the degradation of ether glycols as E2P, M2P,
229 but no empirical evidences have been reported so far.

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230 Fig. 3a illustrates the evolution of the OLR and the RE of E2P in both reactors. The
231 RE of E2P was very low in the beginning, at 21% and 16% for R1 and R2, respectively,
232 but gradually increased to around 80% for both reactors after 40-50 days of exposure to
233 E2P. Generally, longer adaptation periods had been reported for similar solvents.
234 Traverso-Soto et al. (2016) needed 169 days to reach 99.7% of anaerobic
235 biodegradation of alcohol ethoxylates in anaerobic degradation assays with marine
236 sediments. A longer adaptation period for another glycol ether such as M2P was also
237 observed by Lafita et al. (2015), who reported a 34-day acclimatization period for
238 degrading more than 50% of M2P. In a recent study (Lafita et al., 2017), the time
239 required to obtain 80% of removal of M2P was shortened to 22 days when chitosan was
240 supplemented. In the present study, the acclimatization period for removing over 50%
241 of E2P lasted only 11 and 16 days for R1 and R2, respectively. This shorter
242 acclimatization period could be explained by taking into account the different substrate
243 and the slightly lower OLR of the glycol ether used in comparison with previous
244 studies. Besides, during these first weeks of exposure to E2P, acetone and isopropanol
245 were transitorily observed in the effluents of both reactors. The appearance of these
246 byproducts indicates the amenability of E2P to anaerobic treatment and sheds some
247 light on the mechanism of degradation as discussed further below.

248 The OLR of E2P was doubled to $10.6 \text{ kg COD m}^{-3}\text{d}^{-1}$ at stage S-III (Table 1),
249 reaching an average total load of $54.1 \text{ kg COD m}^{-3}\text{d}^{-1}$, which resulted in a decrease of
250 the global RE to around 92% for both reactors (Fig. 2). This decline can be essentially
251 attributed to the decrease in the RE of E2P down to 70%, as shown in Fig. 3a,
252 indicating that the presence of E2P in the system has no observable effect on the
253 ethanol's RE.

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254 At stage S-IV, the average of the total OLR was maintained at around 50 kg COD
255 $\text{m}^{-3}\text{d}^{-1}$ (similar to stages S-II and S-III), but a ternary mixture of ethanol, E2P, and M2P,
256 with a mass ratio of 8:1:1, was used as the organic substrate. At this stage, the
257 performance of both reactors barely changed in terms of the global RE (Fig. 2), as well
258 as the RE of E2P in comparison to the previous stage (S-III). The RE of M2P at the end
259 of S-IV was practically complete as shown in Fig. 3b. Even from the first day of
260 exposure to this compound, the RE of M2P was very high ($> 85\%$) in both reactors,
261 indicating no significant adaptation period for metabolizing this compound. This result
262 could be attributed to the fact that both glycol ethers are degraded through the same
263 mechanism; therefore, the adaptation period for M2P degradation is negligible for a
264 system degrading E2P. As in the case of E2P, degradation byproducts were detected in
265 the effluent during the first days of exposure to M2P (acetone and methanol in this
266 case). Regarding the biodegradability of E2P and M2P, the RE is greater for M2P
267 (almost 100%), which could be related to the substrate's accessibility to the active
268 center of the enzyme, as an M2P molecule is smaller than an E2P molecule. Therefore,
269 the results suggest that the use of M2P would be preferable to E2P as a retarder additive
270 if an anaerobic system is considered for the effluent treatment configuration of the
271 packaging printing facility.

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272 A noticeable conductivity increase to 7.48 mS cm^{-1} and 7.65 mS cm^{-1} for R1 and R2,
273 respectively, was observed at the end of S-V, the stage in which no feeding and no
274 recirculation were applied to the system. This conductivity increase above the typical
275 value in both reactors, around 5.50 mS cm^{-1} , was caused by the increase in ammonium
276 and phosphate concentrations as a consequence of a lysis phenomenon during the
277 starvation period. From a mass balance and considering the cell content of nitrogen and
278 phosphorus, the total biomass decay during this period can be estimated: 52.2 g and

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279 66.0 g for R1 and R2, respectively. This higher increase in nitrogen and phosphorus
280 concentration in R2 than in R1 reflects the AHR system's (R2) greater biomass
281 retention capacity. Because during this period (S-V), no feeding was applied, the cell
282 growth can be neglected, and the concentration of microorganisms (X) can be related to
283 the microorganism concentration before the starvation period (X_0) from a mass balance,
284 as shown in the following equation:

$$X = X_0 \exp(-bt)$$

285 where b is the decay coefficient of biomass, and t denotes the duration of the starvation
286 period. The calculated decay coefficients were 0.0024 d^{-1} and 0.0022 d^{-1} for R1 and R2,
287 respectively. These values are quite similar to the decay coefficients obtained by Wu et
288 al. (1995) with methanogenic granules that previously degraded VFA at 22°C (between
289 0.0015 and 0.0028 d^{-1}).

290 During the restartup, at stage S-VI, conductivity decreased after 4 days to the
291 habitual values, and the OLR was gradually increased from 15.9 to $40.7 \text{ kg COD m}^{-3}\text{d}^{-1}$,
292 with the same feeding composition as in stage S-IV. Both reactors showed a high total
293 RE, 95% for R1 (EGSB) and 94% for R2 (AHR), indicating that a typical industrial
294 long starvation period (> 30 days) does not negatively affect the biomass activity. The
295 glycol ethers' REs were high since the beginning of stage S-VI, 100% for M2P (Fig. 3b)
296 and 77% for E2P (Fig. 3a) in both reactors, so no adaptation period was observed
297 despite the biomass not being exposed to these compounds for more than 40 days.

298 At stage S-VII, the average total OLR was $45.9 \text{ kg COD m}^{-3}\text{d}^{-1}$ (Table 1), but the
299 feeding composition was changed to a ternary mixture of ethanol, E2P, and M2P with a
300 mass ratio of 7:1:2. In both reactors, the total RE was maintained at a high value, similar
301 to the previous stage (Fig. 2). Moreover, M2P was completely removed despite its

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302 increase in OLR, indicating that the levels of M2P concentration used in the experiment
303 did not affect the performance of the reactors. Regarding the REs of E2P (Fig. 3a), these
304 reached 76% and 80% for R1 and R2, respectively, until day 315 when the pall rings in
305 the hybrid reactor (R2) were replaced by clean ones to avoid clogging problems in the
306 filter media. After the replacement, the RE of E2P for R2 dropped to 65%, and the
307 average concentration of VFA in the effluent increased from negligible values to 68.5
308 mg CH₃COOH L⁻¹, while in the EGSB reactor, it only amounted to 14.6 mg CH₃COOH
309 L⁻¹. The decrease in the E2P's RE and the increase in VFA after the replacement of the
310 packaging material showed that a not quite significant part of the R2 activity was related
311 to the active biomass associated with the packed fraction of the reactor.

312 The methane average and standard deviation (SD) yield in R1 was $0.324 \pm 0.051 \text{ m}^3$
313 CH₄ kg COD_{degraded}⁻¹ and in R2, it was $0.318 \pm 0.049 \text{ m}^3 \text{ CH}_4 \text{ kg COD}_{\text{degraded}}^{-1}$,
314 indicating no significant difference between both reactors in the methane production.

315 The evolution of methane production can be found in the supplementary material (Fig.
316 S.7). The average and SD proportion of methane in the biogas was $82.4 \pm 2.6 \%$ and
317 $83.0 \pm 2.9 \%$ for R1 and R2, respectively, with a presence of H₂S below 130 ppm_v.

318 Narra et al. (2014) reported a methane yield between 0.12 and $0.16 \text{ m}^3 \text{ CH}_4 \text{ kg}$
319 COD_{degraded}⁻¹ when working with anaerobic hybrid reactors that treated the wastewater
320 of mild alkali-treated rice straw in ethanol fermentation process. This low yield could be
321 due to the different substrate used. Treating more similar substrates such as solvents that
322 included ethanol, acetone, propanol, and methanol, Enright et al. (2009) obtained
323 methane yields between 0.11 and $0.35 \text{ m}^3 \text{ CH}_4 \text{ kg COD}_{\text{degraded}}^{-1}$, within the range of
324 those obtained in the present study for both reactors.

325 Since acetone was detected as a key intermediate product of anaerobic
326 biodegradation of glycol ethers, an EGSB reactor was fed with this solvent and ethanol

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327 (1:1 mass ratio) to shed light on the mechanism. Fig. 4 shows the evolution of the
328 organic compounds detected in the effluent of R3. The acetone concentration was quite
329 high in the beginning of the trial, but since day 9, the concentration gradually decreased,
330 and the system practically reached complete degradation (98%) of this compound on
331 day 21. These results showed that the biomass needed an adaptation period to remove
332 acetone, as what occurred with E2P, but in this case, the adaptation period was shorter
333 than in the case of E2P, indicating that acetone could be more readily biodegradable
334 than E2P. Thus, experimental evidence seems to point out that the first step of the
335 cleavage to alcohol and acetone could be considered the controlling step for the
336 biodegradation of glycol ethers. This hypothesis would be reinforced, considering the
337 detection of negligible amounts of acetone and/or isopropanol in the effluent found in
338 the experimental series with R1 and R2 (these compounds were only briefly detected
339 when the glycol ethers were first fed into the bioreactors). Furthermore, isopropanol
340 was identified in the effluent of bioreactor R3, as shown in Fig. 4. The appearance of
341 isopropanol in a system treating acetone was explained by Tonouchi (2004) and Zellner
342 and Winter (1987), who concluded that isopropanol could be produced from acetone in
343 the presence of hydrogen, with a reversible reaction. Additionally, Vermorel et al.
344 (2017) observed a significant presence of acetone, besides isopropanol, in the effluent of
345 a laboratory-scale anaerobic CSTR that treated synthetic wastewater with ethanol and
346 isopropanol as organic substrates. This observation would support the hypothesis of the
347 reversibility of the transformation between isopropanol and acetone.

348 **3.2. Anaerobic mechanism of ether cleavage**

349 The mechanism of the anaerobic ether cleavage is not well established yet, although
350 it is suggested that intracellular enzymes depending on cobalamin are involved in this
351 process (Frings et al., 1992). The most accepted mechanism implies a double H/OH

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352 interchange (hydroxyl shift) resulting in the *gem*-diol that rapidly collapses to a
353 carbonyl or a keto group (Speranza et al., 2002). As previously described, the identified
354 byproducts during the first days of the biomass exposure to E2P were acetone and
355 isopropanol, while acetone and methanol were identified in the case of M2P. By
356 analogy with the hydroxyl-shift mechanism of ether excision for anaerobic ether
357 cleavage (White et al., 1996), the theoretical byproducts should be ethanol and acetone
358 from E2P degradation and methanol and acetone from M2P degradation (Lafita et al.,
359 2015). In the case of E2P, no ethanol was observed in the effluent as a readily
360 biodegradable substrate. In any case, as a main substrate, ethanol could not have been
361 attributed as an intermediate product of degradation. On the other hand, the presence of
362 isopropanol could be related to the formation of acetone as it was corroborated with the
363 R3 reactor performance, as previously described. Thus, acetone together with the
364 hydrogen can make the conversion to isopropanol possible, explaining the appearance
365 of this compound in the effluent.

366 In the case of M2P, the presence of methanol was briefly detected in the effluent of
367 both bioreactors (R1 and R2) after M2P was added to the influent. However,
368 isopropanol was not observed because at this phase of the study, the biomass was
369 already well adapted after more than 100 days of degrading E2P; thus, the formed
370 isopropanol should be undetectable by the equipment. Therefore, the hypothetical
371 mechanism schematized in Fig. 5 would explain the presence of the detected organics in
372 the effluent of the reactors. Regarding acetone, its degradation to methane and CO₂ was
373 reported to be the first case in which acetate is the only intermediate transferred between
374 a fermenting bacterium and a methanogen (Platen and Shink, 1987). According to these
375 authors, acetone is first carboxylated to acetoacetate by condensation with CO₂, from
376 which acetate is formed and then transferred to *Methanosateia* sp. (formerly

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377 *Methanothrix sp.*). Methanol can be directly utilized as a carbon and energy source by
378 several species of methanogens and acetogens.

379 **3.3. Biomass retention capacity of AHR and EGSB reactor**

380 Granular and non-granular accumulated solids of each stage collected from the
381 effluent of reactors R1 and R2 can be found in Table 3, and the evolution of total
382 accumulated solids of both reactors are plotted in Fig. 6, which shows that during stage
383 S-I, the solids in the effluent of R1 were considerably higher than in R2, reaching 73.2 g
384 and 29.0 g of accumulated solids, respectively. In the beginning of S-II, the solids
385 collected from both effluents were similar, but from day 133 to day 161, a granular
386 sludge flotation occurred in R1. Therefore, the accumulated solids in the effluent
387 increased considerably with respect to R2, where no granular sludge flotation was
388 registered. Thus, during this stage, 255.0 g of solids were collected from R1 and only
389 109.0 g from R2. During stage S-III, the solids in the effluent were also slightly higher
390 in the EGSB reactor (28.3 g) than in the AHR (20.1 g). Anaerobic granular sludge
391 flotation was observed in the systems (stage S-IV), reaching 45.9 g and 36.5 g of
392 accumulated solids for R1 and R2, respectively. It is important to clarify that the sludge
393 flotation observed has not been a total breakdown that had led to a complete wash out as
394 those described extensively in literature (Macarie et al., 2017; Yoda and Nishimura,
395 1997; Lafita et al., 2015). In fact, if the leakage of solids is quantified in reference to the
396 effluent flow, the average outlet concentration of reactor R1 in stage S-II (stage and
397 reactor most unfavorable in terms of leakage of solids) is 228 g SST m⁻³ which can be
398 considered as a normal value for this kind of anaerobic systems.

399 After the shut-down period (S-V), when feeding was resumed, 20.0 g of solids in
400 total were collected from R2, while only 13.8 g were washed out from R1 during the

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401 first week of stage S-VI. This unusually larger amount of biomass washed out from R2
402 could be explained by the lysis that occurred during the starvation period; as more
403 biomass was retained by R2 than by R1, more granules were proportionally broken in
404 R2, yielding greater biomass washout. The last two stages also showed greater washout
405 from R1, in accordance with the global experimental trend. At the end of the
406 experiment, the accumulated solids collected in the effluent were 563.2 g and 293.7 g
407 for R1 and R2, respectively. This difference shows the AHR's (R2) higher capacity to
408 retain biomass, supporting the study of Borja et al. (1995), who reported that the
409 packing of a hybrid anaerobic reactor significantly enhanced the retention of active
410 biomass treating slaughterhouse wastewater. Furthermore, Guiot and van den Berg
411 (1985) demonstrated that the AHR's biomass retention capacity was between 1.5 and
412 2.8 times higher than those of other bioreactor configurations such as the UASB or the
413 anaerobic baffled reactor.

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414 The significant improvement in the biomass retention capacity of the hybrid system
415 (R2) was not reflected in its performance since no significant differences in the REs of
416 the different compounds were observed over the experimental period. Only slightly
417 more stable and lower concentrations of VFA were observed in the effluent of R2.

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418 In previous research, episodes of biomass flotation in the AHR had been attributed
419 to lipid adsorption in granules (Belançon et al., 2010), but as no lipids were present in
420 the feeding of the present study, the biomass flotation produced during stages S-II and
421 S-IV had to be caused by other factors. Furthermore, in the AHR, no biomass flotation
422 was observed during stage S-II, probably due to the higher capacity to retain biomass.
423 However, the episode of anaerobic granular sludge flotation observed in the AHR at
424 stage S-IV indicated that the filter was highly clogged and close to its maximum
425 retention capacity. This fact can also be observed in Table 3 where, in addition to the

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426 absolute values of the leakage of solids from each reactor, the ratios of the solids in the
427 effluent between control EGSB (R1) and AHR (R2) have been included (granular, non-
428 granular, and total solids). The ratio of the total solids (R1/R2) decreased over the
429 experimental period from 2.5 at stage S-I to 1.1 at stage S-VI, and then, at stage S-VII,
430 it increased again to 2.11 when the packing material was replaced by new and clean
431 polyethylene rings. The decrease in the ratio at every stage was even higher if only
432 granular solids were considered—from 5.6 at stage S-II to 1.1 at stage S-VI, and then,
433 after the replacement of the packing material, the ratio increased again to 4.0 at stage S-
434 VII. In contrast, the non-granular solids (suspended solids) collected from both systems
435 were not significantly different at each of the stages studied (the ratio varied from 1.2 to
436 0.6). These results indicated that the packing material selectively retained the granular
437 biomass versus the solids in suspension. Furthermore, the recovered capacity to retain
438 the solids after the replacement of the packing material suggested that the filter was
439 clogged; thus, to maintain proper performance, it should be periodically cleaned or
440 replaced. It seems that the leakage of granules would be related with regular discharge
441 of surplus biomass in normal operation as reported by Pereboom et al (1994). Likewise,
442 Hulshoff Pol et al. (2014) affirmed that light sludge is separated from mature granules
443 using the rapid upward velocity of EGSB reactor. This selective wash-out, resulting in
444 an increased growth of retained (heavier) sludge agglomerates would be crucial for the
445 granulation process (Lim and Kim, 2004). Thus, it is interesting to highlight that the
446 observed leakage throughout the experimental series has not had significant influence
447 with the performance of the EGSB reactor. Even more interesting is that no difference
448 has been observed between the performance of both systems (control EGSB and AHR)
449 for any stage, which would indicate that the activity of the excess sludge (that was

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450 retained in the case of the AHR system) was practically negligible and no comparable to
451 the activity of retained granules.

452 As a resume, the main advantages and disadvantages of the AHR in comparison
453 with the EGSB observed in this long-term study have been synthesized in Table 4.

454

455 **4. Practical applications and future perspective**

456 The present work is part of a broader research related to the industrial
457 implementation of anaerobic bioscrubber, an innovative system for the control of VOC
458 emissions that is capable to transform solvents into bioenergy (Waalkens et al., 2015).
459 A pilot-scale study of this technology, composed of a packed scrubber and an EGSB
460 reactor of 8.7 m³ treating on-site emissions from a packaging printing facility, showed
461 to be an effective solution for VOC emission control (Bravo et al., 2017). In this
462 context, the results obtained from the present work, based on the acquired knowledge
463 about the retention of the biomass and the anaerobic degradation of glycol-ethers, will
464 allow extending the horizons of practical application of the anaerobic bioscrubber.

465 With regard to the packing printing sector, given the general tendency of packaging
466 manufacturing firms to move nearer to their customers, investment potentials for
467 developing countries abound in this sector. The appeal of products from the developing
468 Southern economies to their Northern and Western markets will have to be extended to
469 their packaging (FAO, 2014). As a result of this sector's trend to install the facilities at
470 point of origin, the demand for these VOCs control systems is expected to be on the
471 rise.

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472 The current research lines are focused in the study of the dynamics of the microbial
473 communities and their interrelation with the bioreactor operation, including its response
474 to starvation periods. On the other hand, the increase of the feasibility of this technology
475 by using a more available and economic source of anaerobic sludge (e.g. from
476 municipal waste water treatment plant) is being investigated.

477

478 5. Conclusions

479 Granular anaerobic treatment was shown to be a feasible technology for the
480 biodegradation of ethanol-glycol ether mixtures such as E2P and M2P after a short
481 period of acclimatization. Of the two systems tested, the AHR showed a higher solid
482 retention capacity than the EGSB but did not result in the AHR's improved
483 performance. Both systems could completely remove M2P (M2P OLR of 8.3 kg COD
484 m⁻³ d⁻¹) and 70% of the E2P (E2P OLR of 10.6 kg COD m⁻³ d⁻¹). The detected
485 byproducts allowed clarifying the degradation pathways of the studied glycol ethers.

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Fig. 1. Diagram of the EGSB reactor (R1) and AHR (R2) with numbered parts: 1) Feed, 2) Glass balls, 3) Effective volume, 4) Packing material, 5) Effluent, 6) Biogas, 7) Recirculation, 8) Gas seal.

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646 **Fig. 2.** Evolution of total OLR and COD removal efficiency of EGSB reactor (R1) and AHR
647 (R2).

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652 **Fig. 3.** Evolution of glycol ethers OLR and COD removal efficiency of EGSB reactor (R1) and
 653 AHR (R2), a) E2P OLR and E2P removal efficiency, b) M2P OLR and M2P removal
 654 efficiency.

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659 **Fig. 4.** Evolution of intermediate compounds' concentration found in the effluent in the reactor
660 R3 treating the ethanol-acetone mixture with an average inlet COD concentration of 11.2 ± 1.5
661 g L^{-1} .

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664 **Fig. 5.** Proposed mechanism for the anaerobic degradation of 1-ethoxy-2-propanol, including
665 isopropanol (IPA) formation from acetone.

Fig. 6. Accumulated suspended solids in the effluent of EGSB reactor (R1) and AHR (R2).

Table 1. Operation conditions for the EGSB reactor (R1) and AHR (R2). Average values and Standard deviation.

Stage	S-I	S-II	S-III	S-IV	S-V	S-VI	S-VII
Time, d	0-90	91-202	203-221	222-230	231-271	272-305	306-335
COD, g L ⁻¹	3.9 to 18.8	18.9 ± 3.0	21.6 ± 3.8	19.5 ± 2.1	-	6.3 to 16.3	18.5 ± 1.9
OLR, kg COD m ⁻³ d ⁻¹	9.1 to 47.0	47.4 ± 7.4	54.1 ± 9.5	48.8 ± 5.1	-	15.9 to 40.7	46.2 ± 4.8
E2P, g COD L ⁻¹	0.0	2.0 ± 0.3	4.2 ± 0.3	2.4 ± 0.9	-	0.7 to 2.1	1.9 ± 0.2
E2P OLR, kg COD m ⁻³ d ⁻¹	0.0	5.1 ± 0.8	10.6 ± 0.7	6.1 ± 2.3	-	1.7 to 5.3	4.8 ± 0.6
M2P, g COD L ⁻¹	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.9 ± 0.1	-	0.6 to 1.9	3.3 ± 0.4
M2P OLR, kg COD m ⁻³ d ⁻¹	0.0	0.0	0.0	4.8 ± 0.2	-	1.5 to 4.7	8.3 ± 1.1

Table 2. Macronutrient and micronutrient supplementation influent.

Compound	Dose, mg g ⁻¹ COD	Compound	Dose, mg g ⁻¹ COD
NH ₄ Cl	15.7	H ₃ BO ₃	0.1143
Yeast extract	7.5	EDTANa	0.100
KCl	6.1	(NH ₄) ₂ Mo ₇ O ₂₄ ·4H ₂ O	0.0625
(NH ₄) ₂ HPO ₄	5.6	Al ₂ O ₃	0.0595
FeCl ₃ ·6H ₂ O	0.4208	NiSO ₄ ·6H ₂ O	0.0447
CoCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O	0.1615	CuCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O	0.0134
MnCl ₂ ·4H ₂ O	0.1441	ZnSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	0.132

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677 **Table 3.** Accumulated suspended solids (SS) in the effluent from each reactor in the different
 678 stages

	Stage:	S-I	S-II	S-III	S-IV	S-VI	S-VII
Non-granular solids (g)	EGSB	73,1	101,2	17,3	6,7	15,0	15,4
	AHR	29,0	81,5	16,6	7,1	12,2	27,5
Granular solids (g)	EGSB	< 0,1	153,8	11,0	39,2	39,1	91,3
	AHR	< 0,1	27,5	3,5	29,4	36,5	22,9
Ratio SS _{EGSB} /SS _{AHR}	Non-granular	2,52	1,24	1,04	0,94	1,24	0,56
	Granular	-	5,59	3,14	1,34	1,07	3,98
	Total	2,52	2,34	1,40	1,26	1,11	2,12

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680 **Table 4.** Advantages/disadvantages of the AHR in comparison with the EGSB system.

Advantages
- Higher solid retention capacity
Disadvantages
- AHR increases to some extent the operational complexity of the treatment
- Increasing biomass retention in the upper packed filter can lead to clogging
- Slight increase in the cost of capital of the system

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Supplementary Material:

Fig. S.1. Evolution of pH in the effluent of the EGSB reactor (R1) and AHR (R2).

Fig. S.2. Evolution of conductivity in the effluent of the EGSB reactor (R1) and AHR (R2).

Fig. S.3. Evolution of volatile fatty acid (VFA) concentration in the effluent of the EGSB reactor (R1) and AHR (R2).

Fig. S.4. Evolution of COD inlet concentration for both reactors and the COD outlet concentration in the effluent of the EGSB reactor (R1) and AHR (R2).

Fig. S.5. Evolution of E2P inlet concentration for both reactors and the E2P outlet concentration in the effluent of the EGSB (R1) and AHR (R2).

Fig. S.6. Evolution of M2P inlet concentration for both reactors and the M2P outlet concentration in the effluent of the EGSB reactor (R1) and AHR (R2).

Fig. S.7. Evolution of the methane flow rate of the EGSB reactor (R1) and AHR (R2) and COD inlet concentration for both reactors.